

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: COMPAORE****FIRST NAME: RODRIGUE W.****PROGRAM CODE: DCTD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 0%

The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on Windows 11 Enterprise.

List 5 to 7 key concepts with page numbers in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. Academic writing (EUCLID 2021, 7-12)
2. Style guides (EUCLID 2021, 40)
3. American vs. British English (EUCLID 2021, 24-32)
4. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 33-39)
5. Latin abbreviations and expressions (EUCLID 2021, 58-62)

WRITING A GOOD ACADEMIC DOCUMENT

1) INTRODUCTION

The period one coursepack ACA-401D provides students with writing, punctuation, and plagiarism basics. It introduces them to the style rules that will strengthen their writing ability to international academic standards. This course, offered by EUCLID, has equipped me to tackle quality schooling by bringing me up to date with existing standards in research, writing methodology, and the requirements and techniques of writing publishable-grade academic papers internationally.

This study period gives the student the necessary foundations to have all the understanding required not only for the period concerned but also to save time for the rest of his schooling.

This response paper will cover critical aspects of academic writing, including style guides, the differences between American and British English, strategies for avoiding plagiarism, and the appropriate use of Latin expressions. I will first explain my understanding of academic essay writing, style guides, English variants, avoiding plagiarism skills, and the use of Latin abbreviations and expressions.

2) THE ACADEMIC WRITING

An academic essay or writing is non-fictional writing for academic purposes (EUCLID 2021, 7). Writing an academic essay is a fundamental skill students develop through the course. I understand from the course text that this exercise requires a structured form of writing that demands critical thinking, analysis, and the ability to present arguments or ideas in a coherent and organized manner.

First, it's essential to identify the central thesis and specific requirements. If I do not have a main thesis, I must look for one (EUCLID 2021, 13). I must use reliable sources such as academic journals, books, and reliable websites to gather information and evidence to support my arguments. Based on my research, I must develop a plan to guide my essay's overall structure and content. Having a plan for going about the essay is very important (EUCLID 2021, 7).

The structure of my essay should include an introduction, a body, and a conclusion (EUCLID 2021, 10). The introduction should be attractive, provide background information, and present my thesis statement. This preamble should capture the reader's attention and provide a roadmap for the essay. The essay's body should consist of several paragraphs, each presenting a distinct argument. I must begin each paragraph with an introductory sentence. Each part of my work should have a clear purpose and support the thesis statement (EUCLID 2021, 11). A solid academic essay involves critical analysis and evaluation of the topic. I must avoid making unsupported assertions and instead provide thoughtful analysis and interpretation of the evidence I present.

Finally, I must conclude my essay by summarizing my main points and reaffirming my thesis. I should avoid introducing new information in the conclusion and end it concisely and forcefully. I must take the time to reread out loud (writing that does not sound right will not read right) (EUCLID 2021, 14) and edit my essay for clarity, grammar, spelling, and punctuation.

3) THE STYLE GUIDE

Going through this course made me realize that style guides are often associated with specific types of writing, such as technical writing, business writing, journalism, and online writing. I must ensure that my writing style is consistent in each case. EUCLID recommends the Chicago Rule of Style (Turabian), but other internationally recognized Rules are fine (EUCLID 2021, 41).

This methodological approach is taught to allow the contribution of multiple authors while ensuring that the student's final work does not necessarily reflect the author's style but rather that of the publication, faculty, or university.

Style can cover many aspects, including sentence length, manuscript layout, font use, depth of treatment, spelling issues, readability, use of abbreviations, accepted

terminology, symbols, language preferences, paragraph structure, numbering, and indentation. Etc. This list could be longer, as every publication, every company, and every author find stylistic elements in their texts. From this list, I have learned that creative copywriters may only bother with some of these elements, whereas writers might consider all these aspects in their daily work.

The style guide is, therefore, a valuable tool for the Euclid University student in me. It could help me save money on proofreading and editing.

4) THE USE OF ENGLISH VARIANTS

Regarding the use of American or British English, I have understood the differences in spelling and punctuation. I have learned to use the rules specific to each variant of English, whether it's the spelling of words, the use of capital letters, quotation marks, commas, semicolons, etc.

The choice between American and British English in essay writing depends on several factors, including the intended audience, the academic institution's guidelines, and personal preference. Some universities or specific departments may have guidelines specifying which English variant to use. In the case of EUCLID, I am given the choice of which version to use. That said, the most crucial aspect is to maintain consistency throughout my essay. Whichever English variant I choose, I must follow the rules and conventions consistently to preserve the clarity and professionalism of my essay. I must avoid mixing American and British English spelling, vocabulary, and punctuation in the same document.

Through this course, I have learned that there are language conventions for the different variants: American English and British English have some spelling, vocabulary, and punctuation differences. For example, "color" (American) vs. "colour" (British), "center" (American) vs. "centre" (British), or "organization" (American) vs. "organisation" (British).

5) AVOID PLAGIARISM

Plagiarism is using another's work, ideas, or words without proper attribution (EUCLID 2021, 34). The course establishes that plagiarism generally takes two forms. Whatever the form, plagiarism is unacceptable (EUCLID 2021, 14). Plagiarism occurs when I use words from the source without using quotation marks (EUCLID 2021, 34). So, to copy words from a source, I must use quotation marks, not just the footnote.

Only references guard against plagiarism, which is a serious academic offense (EUCLID 2021, 11). When I use ideas, concepts, or information from other sources, I must cite them correctly using an appropriate citation system, such as APA, MLA, or Chicago. I must include a complete list of references at the end of my writing assignment. Instead of copying and pasting from a source text, ACA-401D recommends that I practice

paraphrasing and summarizing to express ideas in my own words (paraphrases are the ideas and information an author has produced on a topic but written in your own words) (EUCLID 2021, 36). To do this, I must fully understand the content and reformulate the information while citing the source. I must not provide a paraphrase too close to the source.

However, plagiarism occurs when I repeat ideas without footnoting the source. When I quote an author's phrase or passage verbatim, I must use quotation marks (EUCLID 2021, 47) to indicate that the text is a direct quotation. I can use Grammarly's plagiarism detection tool to check my work before submitting it. This tool can identify similarities between your work and other sources, allowing me to correct potential plagiarism problems before finalizing my writing.

Penalties for plagiarism can range from a poor grade to failure of the course. I should, therefore, avoid plagiarism and take the time to revise my prose.

6) THE USE OF LATIN EXPRESSIONS

In business, formal, and technical writing, use the English equivalent of the abbreviation to avoid misinterpretation by your readers (EUCLID 2021, 59). Latin expressions are often used in the academic field, enabling complex concepts to be expressed precisely and concisely. They can be used to describe principles, laws, theories, or methods that are widely known and understood by the academic community. Their use reflects tradition and respect for academic standards. The ACA-401D course material presents numerous Latin expressions, such as "in situ," "et al.," "ad hoc," or "a priori," which are commonly used in academic literature and are recognized by researchers worldwide. Such expressions facilitate understanding and communication between researchers from different cultures and languages. Since Latin is considered a dead language, its use in the academic context avoids ambiguities or differences in translations from one language to another.

On the other hand, their use can add a touch of formality to my writing, making it look more professional and academic. However, excessive or inappropriate use of Latin expressions can make my work difficult to read and understand for readers unfamiliar with these terms. So, I must find a balance and use them judiciously, making sure that they are clear and relevant to the content of my research. Ultimately, the use of Latin expressions is a matter of personal choice that must fit in with and respect for academic conventions.

7) CONCLUSION

In conclusion, as a Ph.D. student, I have developed thorough academic writing skills, style guides, English variants, avoiding plagiarism skills and using Latin abbreviations and expressions. These skills have enabled me to produce high-quality, well-referenced work that complies with EUCLID academic standards.

After rigorous data collection and analysis, I must organize the thesis content logically and coherently, writing concisely and precisely, using appropriate academic language. I need to avoid ambiguities, vague wording, and plagiarism, respect appropriate academic citation and referencing standards, use a specific citation style, and correctly reference all sources used. Finally, proofread the work carefully to identify and correct any errors.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth Edition. Bangui: Euclid University.

Turabian, Kate L., Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, and William T. FitzGerald. 2018. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Ninth edition. Chicago Guides to Writing, Editing, and Publishing. Chicago; London: The University of Chicago Press.

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